

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 21 October 2003

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No 'official' report was issued by the IICD on 21 October 2003. The following is (a draft version) of a statement made by General John de Chastelain at a press conference at Hillsborough, County Down.

"The commission has witnessed a third event in which IRA weapons are put beyond use in accordance with the government scheme and regulations.

The arms comprise light, medium and heavy ordnance and associated munitions.

They include automatic weapons, ammunition, explosives and explosive material.

The quantity of weapons involved was larger than the quantity put beyond use in the previous event.

I do want to make the point - and that is why we have indicated this time - that the amount of arms put beyond use was larger - I would say considerably larger - than the previous event."

Andrew D. Sens, Member of the IICD, added:

"The material put beyond use this morning could have caused death or destruction on a huge scale had it been put to use."

Hillsborough, 21 October 2003

Table with 2 columns: Dublin Office (Dublin Castle, Block M, Ship Street, DUBLIN 2, Tel No: 00 353 (0)1 4780111, Fax No: 00 353 (0)1 4780600) and Belfast Office (Rosepark House, Upper Newtownards Road, BELFAST, BT4 3NX, Tel No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8600, Fax No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8601)

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